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Metal Injection Molding of Cu/CF Composites

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Metal Injection Molding (MIM)

- Complex 3D shape
- Mass Production
- Mechanical Properties

Flow during Injection Molding

Materials flow in one direction

Development of materials and products
using the flow of resin

Realized only with MIM

Cu/CF Composites
Mechanical Properties
Thermal conductivity

Materials

	Copper	Carbon fiber
	Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) showing a dense collection of thin, rod-like carbon fibers. A red scale bar in the bottom right corner indicates 100 micrometers.	
Size	Diameter 9.4 μm	Diameter 7 μm Length 130 μm
Density	8.94 g/cm^3	1.76 g/cm^3

Mixing

(Cu Powder + Carbon Fiber) + Wax based Binder

Fiber (vol%) (mass%)	0	5	10	50
Binder Contents				
35 (vol%)	×	×	×	
40 (vol%)	○ Cu100	○ Cu95	○ Cu90	
50 (vol%)				×
65 (vol%)				○ Cu50

Pellet (Cu50)

Injection Molding

Length 50 mm
Width 5 mm
Thickness 2 mm

Green Compacts

Green Compacts

50 μm

Sintered Compacts

Cu50

Cu90

Cu100

Metallic luster
Shrinkage

Relative Density

Shrinkage

Carbon and Oxygen Contents

Cross Section

100 μm

Cu90

Cu95

Cu100

Changes in Fiber Length

	Mean length (μm)	
Fiber Catalog Measured	130 281	
Pellet	101	
Sintered Cu95	153	
Sintered Cu90	161	